

Brunel
University
London

Brunel University London has a vibrant, rich and dynamic population of staff and students from all over the world. Equality and Diversity strongly underpins our core values outlined within our Strategic Plan.

Although there is a legal case for equality, we strongly believe in the moral case too. It is our intention to support the development of a culture where all may live, study and work without encountering prejudice or discrimination because of their gender, race, disability, sexual orientation, religion, belief or age. We have a vital role to play in preparing our learners to be successful in their life and work in a world which is increasingly diverse and interconnected.

We will continue to develop a culture that is fully committed to equal opportunities and one which represents the diversity of the communities served.

The template for this leaflet is available using the QR code under a CC BY-CC-SA 4.0 licence, and was created by K. Patel, S. Ber, and A. Esposito. This version was edited by AE (CenGEM, Department of Life Sciences, Brunel University London).

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7654652

**HARD WORKING AND SMART,
NOTHING ELSE DEFINES A SCIENTIST.**

**Our Superpower
is You!**

SUPERHEROES IN SCIENCE

word search puzzle

Superheroes in science - word search puzzle

N	S	A	R	L	N	K	F	P	F	E	P	M	L	U	J	O	X	C	Z	N	A	S	U	X
A	Q	T	E	Y	D	E	J	J	D	S	A	M	Q	A	O	S	H	B	R	J	G	F	W	X
I	L	W	E	O	A	S	I	W	S	R	V	W	K	V	T	A	F	F	K	E	Q	G	G	G
V	W	B	I	P	Z	D	I	L	Y	Z	P	O	I	C	R	F	I	M	O	N	D	X	N	V
M	U	P	E	W	H	N	A	A	D	H	Y	T	V	L	J	C	I	R	F	H	K	N	U	R
B	O	S	G	R	K	E	N	R	V	I	D	W	E	Q	M	A	G	S	T	V	A	I	I	O
E	N	H	I	R	T	N	N	I	A	D	V	S	N	P	S	E	P	Q	S	F	F	J	H	X
X	Y	B	E	I	I	E	F	H	M	F	D	I	A	W	W	U	I	Y	U	U	I	F	S	M
O	T	B	D	N	I	O	I	E	A	A	L	K	N	A	K	S	C	S	J	Y	D	J	N	S
N	S	T	G	Q	V	U	D	N	R	W	L	E	S	E	H	E	S	R	T	Z	R	J	E	T
F	B	F	M	H	J	I	E	W	S	H	K	H	A	I	J	Y	Z	E	T	G	K	H	I	D
O	F	S	I	U	R	K	I	R	D	T	I	I	R	H	S	B	W	N	E	D	C	A	H	A
D	C	C	M	Y	R	N	R	Y	O	N	E	L	N	J	C	W	E	T	R	T	R	G	C	I
N	W	G	L	O	J	Y	O	J	G	E	E	I	A	G	F	I	X	I	E	Y	N	A	G	H
W	E	L	S	I	S	Y	L	T	H	Y	Q	N	N	A	D	P	M	E	V	S	W	Q	D	J
Y	A	B	E	N	B	G	O	C	A	A	E	P	O	Y	Y	M	N	M	E	F	U	H	P	T
S	X	A	M	F	P	N	V	N	L	G	M	A	B	H	V	D	L	E	T	X	S	N	J	B
X	L	K	X	N	C	C	N	A	O	D	Z	A	T	C	N	K	V	S	S	J	K	W	J	D
F	M	U	N	A	O	J	N	O	E	S	U	R	D	I	U	F	C	I	E	U	M	J	K	V
V	E	T	R	V	A	T	D	B	B	O	Z	Y	T	Q	R	N	H	L	N	Q	I	W	H	H
H	L	V	T	C	U	A	S	X	F	Q	R	G	N	C	S	O	V	R	R	T	J	Y	A	R
O	E	J	K	R	L	S	U	A	A	F	L	B	Y	F	E	S	R	K	E	Z	Q	K	B	S
R	R	S	I	L	F	L	O	R	E	N	C	E	N	I	G	H	T	I	N	G	A	L	E	V
G	O	N	Y	R	X	D	A	F	B	P	G	A	M	Y	K	H	Y	D	N	K	N	Y	X	Z
N	G	T	R	M	X	D	A	D	A	S	Z	R	O	W	G	R	I	R	Y	V	T	B	D	M

Superhero Achievement or discovery

ALAN TURING	Theoretical computer sciences
FLORENCE NIGHTINGALE	Modern nursing and hospital epidemiology
NEIL DIVINE	Modern understanding of star formation
SALLY RIDE	First American astronaut in space
GEORGE WASHINGTON CARVER	Revolutionized the agricultural economy
ERNEST EVERETT JUST	Pioneered work in cytology and embryology
STEPHEN HAWKING	Pioneered studies of black holes
EDWIN KREBS	Reversible protein phosphorylation
ALBERT EINSTEIN	Understanding of space-time and gravity
CHARLES DARWIN	Theory of natural selection
SHIRLEY ANN JACKSON	Advanced telecommunication systems
CHIEN SHIUNG WU	Pioneer in the field of nuclear physics
LISE MEITNER	Co-discovered nuclear fission
MARY ANNING	Jurassic fossils (ichthyosaurs, plesiosaurus)
JANE GOODALL	Revolutionized the field of primatology
MICHAEL FARADAY	Discovered electromagnetic induction

